

Synthesis and Chemistry of 3-Amino- and 3-Hydrazo-carbonylquinoxalinone Derivatives

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3-Ethoxycarbonyl-2(1*H*)-quinoxalinone (1) reacts with nucleophiles, namely, dimethylamine, diethylamine, *o*-phenylenediamine and/or *p*-phenylenediamine to produce the corresponding 3-*N*-substituted-aminocarbonyl-2(1*H*)-quinoxalinones (3–6). Treatment of 1 with hydrazine hydrate produces the 2(1*H*)-quinoxalinone-3-carbohydrazide (2) with acylating reagents, namely, acetic anhydride, acetic acid or acetyl chloride/pyridine, phenylisothiocyanate, *p*-toluene-sulphonyl chloride and/or diethylmalonate to produce the corresponding 3-β-*N*-substituted-hydrazocarbonyl-2(1*H*)-quinoxalinones (7–10, 12). Condensation of 2 with benzaldehyde, *p*-anisaldehyde, *p*-*N*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde and/or *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde gives the corresponding 3-arylidenehydrazocarbonyl-2(1*H*)-quinoxalinones (11a–d). Treatment of 2 with acetylacetone gives 3-(3,5-dimethylpyrazol-1-yl-carbonyl)-2(1*H*)-quinoxalinone (13). Diazodisation of 2 produces 2(1*H*)-quinoxalinone-3-carboazide (14) which when treated with absolute ethanol and/or *t*-butanol produces the corresponding 3-alkoxycarbonylaminoquinoxalinones (15, 16) and the both cyclise on treatment with hydrazine hydrate into triazinoquinoxaline (17).

Quinoxaline derivatives possess various biological activities¹. In continuation of our work on quinoxaline derivatives², the present study was undertaken to synthesise new series of 3-aminocarbonylquinoxalinones and study their biological activities.

Condensation of *o*-phenylenediamine with diethylbromomalonate in absolute ethanol gave 3,4-dihydro-3-ethoxycarbonyl-2(1*H*)-quinoxalinone³ which was dehydrogenated with selenium dioxide in dry toluene to give 3-ethoxycarbonyl-2(1*H*)-quinoxalinone (1). Treatment of 1 with alkyl and/or aryl amines as nucleophiles, namely, hydrazine hydrate or dimethylamine, diethylamine, *o*-phenylenediamine and/or *p*-phenylenediamine gave the corresponding 3-*N*-substituted-carboxamidyl-2(1*H*)-quinoxalinone, namely, 3-*N*-carbohydrazidyl- (2), 3-*N*-dimethyl- (3), 3-*N*-diethyl- (4), 3-*N*-(*o*-aminophenyl)- (5) and 3-*N*-(*p*-aminophenyl) (6) aminocarbonyl derivatives.

Refluxing 2 with acetic anhydride gave 3-*N*-(α,β-triacetyl)hydrazocarbonyl-2(1*H*)-quinoxalinone (7). However, refluxing 2 with acetyl chloride/pyridine or with glacial acetic acid gave 3-*N*-(β-monoacetyl)hydrazocarbonyl-2(1*H*)-quinoxalinone

1, R = -OC₂H₅

3, R = -N(CH₃)₂

4, R = -N(C₂H₅)₂

5, R = -NHC₆H₄NH₂ (*o*)

6, R = -NHC₆H₄NH₂ (*p*)

7, R = -CO-N(COCH₃)₂

14, R = -N₃

13, R =

2, R = -H

8, R = -COCH₃

9, R = -CS-NHPh

10, R = -SO₂-C₆H₄-CH₃ (*p*)

12, R = -CO-CH₂-COOC₂H₅

15, R = -COOC₂H₅

16, R = -COOC(CH₃)₃

11a, Ar = C₆H₅

11b, Ar = C₆H₄-OCH₃ (*p*)

11c, Ar = C₆H₄-N(CH₃)₂ (*p*)

11d, Ar = C₆H₄-NO₂ (*p*)

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(8). Treatment of 2 with phenylisothiocyanate gave 3-phenylthiosemicarbazocarbonyl-2(1*H*)-quinoxalinone

(9). Treatment of **2** with *p*-toluene sulphonyl chloride gave 3-*N*- β -*p*-toluene sulphonyl hydrazocarbonyl-2(1*H*)-quinoxalinone (**10**). Condensation of **2** in presence of piperidine with aromatic aldehydes such as benzaldehyde, *p*-anisaldehyde, *p*-*N*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde and/or *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde gave the corresponding 3-arylidene hydrazocarbonyl-2(1*H*)-quinoxalinones (**11a-d**) respectively. Treatment of **2** with diethylmalonate gave 3- β -*N*-ethoxycarbonylacetylhydrazocarbonyl-2(1*H*)-quinoxalinone (**12**). However, treatment of **2** with acetylacetone gave the cyclic product, 3-(3,5-dimethylpyrazol-1-yl-carbonyl)-2(1*H*)-quinoxalinone (**13**).

The carbohydrazide (**2**) was treated with nitrous acid to produce 2(1*H*)-quinoxalinone-3-carboazide (**14**). The carboazide (**14**) on thermal Curtius rearrangements by refluxing in absolute ethanol or tertiary butanol gave the corresponding products, 3-ethoxycarbonylamine-2(1*H*)-quinoxalinone (**15**) and 3-tertiary-butylloxycarbonylamino-2(1*H*)-quinoxalinone (**16**) respectively. Both **15** and **16** underwent ring-closure reaction when treated with hydrazine hydrate to give the same product triazino[5,6-*b*]-4(3*H*)-quinoxalinone (**17**). The same product was synthesised through one-pot procedure, on treatment of the azine (**14**) with hydrazine hydrate in presence of either absolute ethanol or dry *t*-butanol as solvent which was assumed to constitute primarily ester formation followed by cyclisation to the triazinone.

Biological activity : As revealed from results of agar-diffusion tests, most examined compounds showed good bactericidal with considerable anti-fungal activity for some.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP3-100, electronic spectra on a Shimadzu 200 spectrophotometer, nmr spectra were recorded on a Varian EM-390 (90 MHz) spectrometer and mass spectra (solid sample) on a MS-902, AET (England) mass spectrometer.

3-Ethoxycarbonyl-2(1*H*)-quinoxalinone (1) : A

mixture of 3,4-dihydro-3-ethoxycarbonyl-2(1*H*)-quinoxalinone³ (2 g, 0.01 mol) and selenium dioxide (5 g) in dry toluene (20 ml) was refluxed for 5 h and the resulting solid was crystallised : ν_{\max} 3180 (NH), 1750 (C=O ester), 1655 (C=O nucleus), 1600 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ (DMSO- d_6) 1.1-1.4 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.2-4.45 (2H, q, CH₂), 7.4 (1H, s, NH), 7.1-7.7 (4H, m, ArH).

2-(1*H*)-Quinoxalinone-3-carbohydrazide (2) : A mixture of **1** (2.18 g, 0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (3 ml; 98%) in ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed for 2 h and the separated solid was crystallised : ν_{\max} 3440-3170 (NH, NH₂), 1690 (C=O hydrazide), 1660 cm^{-1} (C=O nucleus); *m/z* 204 (C₉H₈N₄O₂).

3-*N*-Substituted-aminocarbonyl-2(1*H*)-quinoxalinones (3-6). **General procedure** : A mixture of **1** (0.436 g, 0.002 mol) and the corresponding amine (0.002 mol) (namely, dimethylamine, diethylamine, *o*-phenylenediamine and *p*-phenylenediamine) in ethanol (20 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The separated solids were crystallised : **3** and **4** ν_{\max} 3420 (NH), 1680-1660 cm^{-1} (two C=O); **5** ν_{\max} 3380-3280 (NH, NH₂), 1660-1700 (two C=O), 1600 cm^{-1} (C=N), δ (DMSO- d_6) 7.1 (1H, s, 2 \times NH), 6.5-6.8 (8H, m, ArH), 10.5 (2H, s, NH₂), *m/z* 280 (C₁₅H₁₂N₄O₂); **6** ν_{\max} 3320-3100 (NH, NH₂), 1650-1680 cm^{-1} (two C=O).

3-*N*-(α , β -Triacetyl)hydrazocarbonyl-2(1*H*)-quinoxalinone (7) and 3-*N*-(β -monoacetyl)hydrazocarbonyl-2(1*H*)-quinoxalinone (8) : A mixture of **2** (0.8 g, 0.004 mol) and the corresponding acetylating agent in acetic anhydride (15 ml) was refluxed for 1 h and/or in glacial acetic acid (15 ml) for 3 h. The resulting solids were crystallised : **7** ν_{\max} 3120 (NH), 1750-1670 (three C=O), 1650 cm^{-1} (C=O nucleus); **8** ν_{\max} 3220-3120 (three NH), 1700-1670 cm^{-1} (three C=O).

3-Phenylthiosemicarbazocarbonyl-2(1*H*)-quinoxalinone (9) : A mixture of **2** (2.04 g, 0.01 mol) and phenyl isothiocyanate (1.25 ml, 0.01 mol) in dry pyridine (20 ml) was refluxed for 4 h and the separated solid was crystallised : ν_{\max}

3280–3100 (four NH), 1670 (C=O), 1645 (C=O nucleus), 1600 cm^{-1} (C=N).

3-N- β -p-Toluenesulphonylhydrazocarbonyl-2(1H)-quinoxalinone (10): A mixture of **2** (0.8 g, 0.004 mol) and *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (0.285 g, 0.002 mol) in dry pyridine was refluxed for 2 h and the solid separated was crystallised: ν_{max} 3200–3090 (three NH), 1690 (C=O), 1670 (C=O nucleus), 1590 cm^{-1} (C=N).

3-Arylidenehydrazocarbonyl-2(1H)-quinoxalinones (11a–d). *General procedure*: A mixture of **2** (0.8 g, 0.004 mol) and each of the aromatic aldehyde (0.004 mol) (namely, benzaldehyde, *p*-anisaldehyde, *p*-*N*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde and *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde), in ethanol (20 ml) and piperidine was refluxed for 1 h. The separated solids were crystallised: ν_{max} 3180–3100 (NH), 1710–1650 cm^{-1} (two C=O).

3- β -N-Ethoxycarbonylacetylhydrazocarbonyl-2-(1H)-quinoxalinone (12): A mixture of **2** (0.8 g, 0.004 mol) and diethylmalonate (3 ml) was refluxed for 3 h and the resulting solid was crystallised: ν_{max} 3200–3090 (three NH), 1740 (C=O ester), 1695–1660 cm^{-1} (three C=O), δ (CDCl_3) 1.1–1.3 (3H, t, CH_3), 3.4 (2H, s, CH_2), 4.0–4.3 (2H, q, CH_2CH_3), 7.2–7.9 (5H, m, NH + ArH), 10.9 (1H, s, NH), 11.4 (1H, s, NH).

3-(3,5-Dimethylpyrazol-1-yl-carbonyl)-2(1H)-quinoxalinone (13): A mixture of **2** (0.8 g, 0.004 mol) and acetylacetone (0.004 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) was refluxed for 3 h and the resulting solid was crystallised: ν_{max} 3120 (NH), 1740 (C=O), 1670 cm^{-1} (C=O nucleus).

2(1H)-Quinoxalinone-3-carboazide (14): To a mixture of **2** (2.04 g, 0.1 mol) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (10 ml) was added sodium nitrite solution (14 ml, 0.01 mol) at 0° with stirring for 30 min and the resulting solid was crystallised: ν_{max} 3100 (NH), 2180 (azide), 1710 ($\text{N}_3\text{-C=O}$), 1650 (C=O nucleus), 1610 cm^{-1} (C=N).

*3-Ethoxycarbonylamino-2(1H)-quinoxalinone (15) and 3-*t*-butyloxycarbonylamino-2(1H)-quinoxalinone (16)*: Compound **14** (2.14 g, 0.01 mol) with absolute ethanol (30 ml) or tertiary butanol (30 ml) under reflux for 3 h, gave the products which were crystallised: ν_{max} 1740 (C=O ester), 1675 (C=O nucleus), 1615 (C=N) and also 3440–3380 (two NH) for **15** and 3400–3200 cm^{-1} (two NH) for **16**; **15** δ (CDCl_3) 1.2–1.4 (3H, t, CH_3), 4.1–4.3 (2H, q, CH_2), 7.1–7.6 (4H, m, ArH), 9.1 (1H, s, NH), 12.5 (1H, s, NH); **16** δ (CDCl_3) 1.6 (9H, s, $(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 7.2–7.4 (4H, m, ArH), 8.4 (1H, s, NH), 11.7 (1H, s, NH).

*Triazino[5,6-*b*]-3(4H)-quinoxalinone (17)*: A mixture of **14** (2.14 g, 0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (2 ml) either in absolute ethanol (20 ml) or in *t*-butanol (30 ml) was refluxed for 3 h and the solid separated in each case was filtered and recrystallised; alternatively, the same product was separated on heating **15** and/or **16** with hydrazine hydrate: **17** ν_{max} 3310 (NH), 1670 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) 7.5 (1H, s, NH disappeared on adding D_2O), 7.2–7.8 (4H, m, ArH).

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